

SUCCESS STORIES

Scheduled Tribe Component of ICAR-AICRP on Fruits

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Prakash Patil, S Priya Devi & Sridhar Gutam | ICAR-AICRP on Fruits, Bengaluru

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Papaya Tribal Farmers' Livelihood Security through Papaya Cultivation: A Success Story from Jharkhand

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Challenge

Papaya stands as a crucial fruit crop in Jharkhand, with tribal communities primarily cultivating papaya plants within their backyard gardens. While these homestead-grown papaya fruits are both consumed by the farmers and sold in the market, it's worth noting that scientific papaya cultivation remains relatively undeveloped among the tribal farmers in the state.

Initiative

In order to address this disparity, a significant initiative was launched in 2018-19 by the Farming System Research Centre for Hill and Plateau Region, Ranchi, a part of ICAR RCER, in the Gumla, Ranchi, and Lohardaga districts of Jharkhand. This initiative fell under the Tribal Sub Plan of ICAR's All India Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Fruits. To engage tribal farmers effectively, support from PRADAN (Professional Assistance for Development Action), an NGO specializing in farm livelihoods, was sought to provide essential guidance and assistance.

Initiative Details:

Training and Exposure Visits: Prior to planting, a comprehensive training program consisting of eight sessions was conducted, along with exposure visits for tribal farmers to educate them on the principles of scientific papaya cultivation. These training sessions were strategically held within the farmers' villages, involving approximately 1,300 tribal farmers.

Variety and Planting Technique: The initiative also included technology demonstrations utilizing papaya varieties such as Red Lady, NSC 902, and Ranchi Local. More than 600 tribal farmers engaged in planting these varieties, totaling 30,000 plants. The Ranchi Local variety was particularly favored by farmers due to its hardiness and reduced susceptibility to pests and diseases. However, as Ranchi Local is dioecious, only 50-60% of plants produce fruits. To address this issue, a new planting technique was introduced, involving the placement of three seedlings per pit and the removal of male plants after flowering initiation. This innovation resulted in a remarkable improvement, with 80-90% of plants bearing fruits, leading to a 30-40% increase in overall production. An example of this success can be seen in Mrs. Roopvanti Didi from Dubang village in Lohardaga district, who implemented this method, yielding significant returns.

Micronutrient Application: Micronutrient application, particularly the use of Boron (at 0.3%), was demonstrated among farmers. Boron application, through four sprays, notably reduced flower and fruit drop by 22-35% and increased yields by 15-20%, irrespective of the papaya variety.

Disease Management: Papaya ring spot virus (PRSV) is a prevalent disease in the region. To combat its spread through vectors, an integrated approach was adopted. This approach involved planting disease-free seedlings, avoiding virus host plants such as cucurbits and solanaceous vegetables near papaya fields, weed removal, monthly neem oil sprays, and the use of systemic insecticides. These measures collectively contributed to a significant reduction in PRSV incidence, by up to 50-60%.

Overall, this initiative has not only empowered tribal farmers with valuable knowledge but has also introduced innovative practices to enhance papaya cultivation and mitigate crop-related challenges.

Impact

The initiative has yielded remarkable results, significantly augmenting the income of farmers, with earnings ranging from Rs 1,200 to Rs 175,000. This variance is attributed to factors such as the cultivation area and the implementation of effective management practices. More importantly, the initiative has catalyzed enthusiasm among farmers in neighboring villages, inspiring them to embark on papaya cultivation.

Recognizing the increasing demand for planting materials and the potential for entrepreneurship development among tribal farmers, a decision was made to promote papaya nursery raising in the region through a participatory approach. To facilitate this, a training program on "Improved Papaya Nursery Raising" was conducted, benefitting 16 progressive farmers from Gumla and Lohardaga districts. Essential resources, including poly bags and papaya seeds, were provided to these trainees through the Tribal Sub Plan (TSP) of ICAR-AICRP on Fruits. Below is a table detailing the production of papaya planting material by tribal farmers:

Table 1. Papaya Planting Material Production by Tribal Farmers

Name of Farmer	Village	Block	No. of Plants Produced (2020)	No. of Plants Produced (2021)	No. of Plants Produced (2022)	Income Earned (2020, Rs.)	Income Earned (2021, Rs.)	Income Earned (2022, Rs.)
Roopvanti Devi	Dubang	Kuru	2300	1500	1000	10,000	7,000	6,000
Emlen Kandulina	Kuru	Kuru	2766	3000	4090	32,770	40,500	35,000
Kundi Devi	Kundo	Ghaghra	-	14,000	8400	-	2,00,000	1,84,800
Raj Kapoor	Todar Prakhand Toli	Senha	5200	3100	3200	83,000	62,000	62,500

The additional income generated from the nursery, particularly during the COVID-19 lockdown and the post-lockdown period, has been a significant boon for the farmers. One nursery entrepreneur, Mrs. Kundi Devi, established a link with a Farmer Producer Company (FPC) called Ghaghra Woman Farmer Producer Company Limited for consistent papaya supply to FPC members. Moreover, the profit earned by papaya growers through this program has served as an inspiration for other tribal farmers in the area.

The Government of Jharkhand has also begun promoting papaya cultivation among tribal farmers through various State and Centrally Sponsored Schemes in the past two years. It is expected that with scientific guidance from institutions, scientific papaya cultivation can become a lucrative income generation activity for migrant laborers in the district in the coming years.

Lessons Learned:

1. **Year-Round Cultivation Suitability:** The initiative has revealed that papaya is well-suited for year-round cultivation in Jharkhand. Understanding the local climate and adapting cultivation practices accordingly can ensure a consistent supply of papaya.
2. **Effective Raised Bed Cultivation:** Implementing raised bed cultivation techniques has proven effective for achieving better plant establishment. This approach can improve soil drainage, root development, and overall plant health.
3. **Resilience of Local Varieties:** Local papaya varieties have demonstrated a higher resilience against diseases and pests. This knowledge underscores the importance of preserving and promoting indigenous varieties that are well-adapted to local conditions.
4. **Sustainability through Linkages:** Establishing linkages between nursery entrepreneurs and Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) can contribute to the long-term sustainability of these entrepreneurs. Such partnerships can provide a stable market for their produce, enhancing economic viability.

These lessons emphasize the significance of adapting agricultural practices to local conditions, preserving native crop varieties, and creating sustainable market linkages to support the livelihoods of farmers and nursery entrepreneurs.

Supporting Images

Additional Information:

Research Partners and Donors: The successful implementation of this initiative received support and collaboration from the following research partners and organizations:

- **Farming System Research Centre for Hill and Plateau Region, Ranchi, ICAR Research Complex for Eastern Region:** This research center played a crucial role in coordinating and executing the initiative.
- **Professional Assistance For Development Action (PRADAN) NGO, Lohardaga Team:** PRADAN provided invaluable support in mobilizing and assisting tribal farmers in the field of farm livelihoods.

Links to Supporting Materials:

Here are links to various supporting materials, including media coverage and success stories:

- **Media Coverage on Papaya Cultivation by Krishi Darshan Ranchi:** [Watch Video](#)
- **Success Story Published on ICAR Website:** [Read Story](#)
- **Slideshare Content:** [View Presentation](#)

Source: This information is sourced from ICAR-AICPR on Fruits Ranchi Centre, FSRCHPR, ICAR-RCER, Ranchi.

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Tribal Farmers in Valsad, Gujarat improved their livelihoods with banana farming

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Challenge

Banana is a globally renowned and vital fruit due to its rich nutrient content, offering numerous health benefits. Beyond its nutritional value, it plays a crucial role in the livelihoods of farmers, providing year-round food security and income. The Fruit Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, located in Gandevi, Gujarat, is actively involved in the ICAR-All India Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Fruits. This center, with a history spanning three decades, has developed numerous region-specific technologies aimed at reducing input costs and enhancing productivity and quality in banana cultivation.

The Indian government initiated the Tribal Sub Plan (TSP) to address poverty, unemployment, and income generation among tribal populations. The Dang and several talukas in the Valsad district of South Gujarat are home to over 50% tribal residents. Most of the farmers in these regions are smallholders, cultivating crops such as paddy, green gram, black gram, watermelon, vegetables, sugarcane, and pigeonpea on small landholdings ranging from 1 to 4 hectares. Agriculture and animal husbandry are their primary sources of income, with banana cultivation being relatively minor. The annual income from various crops for these farmers typically ranges from Rs. 0.50 to 1.10 lakh. Due to limited awareness and access to advanced technologies, fruit crop cultivation had been largely neglected.

Initiative

In 2014-15, scientists from the Fruit Research Station in Gandevi surveyed the Valsad district and identified the Kaprada block as a suitable area for banana cultivation. Over the next five years (2014-15 to 2019-20), the center implemented more than 100 Front Line Demonstrations (FLDs) to introduce various technologies to tribal farmers. These demonstrations took place in villages like Khutli, Jamgabhan, Jogvel, Kurgam, and Vadadha, all in the Valsad district. To encourage tribal farmers to adopt banana cultivation with modern technologies, regular farmer meetings, Kisan Goshthi (farmer gatherings), and exposure visits to the Fruit Research Station in Gandevi were organized. The technology demonstrations included the use of tissue-cultured banana plants (cv. Grand Naine), recommended chemical fertilizers, various biofertilizers, organic liquid nutrients, Trichoderma, Pseudomonas, and blue polythene sleeves for protection. Additionally, high-density planting and intercropping with vegetables were showcased to maximize profits during the early stages of banana crop growth. These demonstrations were conducted for 2 to 4 years on individual farmers' fields to assess the impact of different technologies on banana cultivation.

Outputs: The initiative to promote banana cultivation has proven to be successful in increasing the income of tribal farmers when compared to traditional field crops. Thanks to AICRP technology interventions over the past 5-6 years, farmers have achieved bunch yields ranging from 14-20 kg per plant, including ratoon crops, with banana prices ranging from Rs. 6 to 10 per kilogram, depending on the area and management practices. The estimated expenditure for banana cultivation per hectare ranged from Rs. 2.0 to 2.50 lakh, while farmers earned incomes ranging from Rs. 4.00 to 4.80 lakh per hectare. Consequently, tribal farmers could attain a net profit of between Rs. 2.00 to 2.30 lakh per hectare. Furthermore, intercropping vegetables with banana allowed farmers to earn an additional income of Rs. 10,000-15,000 annually without incurring extra costs.

Outcome

The initiative, comprising technology demonstrations and awareness programs, acted as a catalyst, inspiring farmers in neighboring villages to embrace banana cultivation. As a result, banana acreage and production in the Valsad district increased by 20-25% over the past 5-6 years. The region demonstrated significant potential for banana cultivation and marketability compared to other crops. Today, more than 550 young farmers in the Kaprada block of Valsad district are engaged in banana cultivation, experiencing returns that are 30-50% higher than conventional field crop farming. Some of these young farmers have even ventured into banana purchasing and marketing in other areas. Overall, banana cultivation has transformed the social and economic status of these banana growers, leaving them content and economically empowered.

Impact

In a recent development since 2020-21, the introduction of macro-propagated banana plants alongside tissue-cultured plants has been initiated at existing tribal farmers' fields. Encouraged by the results of macro-propagated plants, farmers have expressed a strong demand for these plants for cultivation. Given the cost-effectiveness of macro-propagated plants and the potential for entrepreneurship, the Gandevi center conducted two on-farm training sessions on "Banana Macro-propagation Technology," benefiting 18 farmers, including tribal farmers. As a result, four tribal farmers from Khutli village signed MoUs for the production of banana macro-propagated plants on their farms in November 2021, and others are also considering adopting this technology in the tribal district.

Photos

Table 2. Year-wise yield and income data of different farmers from banana cultivation in the Kaprada block of Valsad district, Gujarat:

Sr. No.	Name of Farmer and Address	Total Area (ha)	Total Income from Field Crops (Rs.)	Year	Area Under Banana Crop (ha)	Total No. of Banana Plants Supplied	Total Yield of Banana (kg)	Total Income from Banana (Rs.)
1	Gulabbhai Babubhai Chaudhary At-Vadadha	1.20	45,000-50,000	2016-17	0.20	600	10,000	70,000
				2017-18	0.65	2000	31,250	2,50,000
				2018-19	0.40	1200	14,285	1,00,000
				2019-20	0.32	1000	12,142	85,000
2	Kishorbhai Jamsubhai Gamit At-Vadadha	1.50	65,000-75,000	2016-17	0.16	500	11,666	70,000
				2017-18	0.23	700	12,142	85,000
3	Jinabhai Bhanjubhai Bhoya At-Jamgabhan	3.60	70,000-90,000	2016-17	0.20	600	11,666	70,000
				2017-18	0.23	700	8,333	50,000
				2018-19	0.26	800	13,571	95,000
				2019-20	0.32	1000	12,142	85,000
4		3.20	85,000-92,000	2015-16	0.32	1000	19,444	1,75,000

	Kantubhai Somabhai Bhoya At Jamgabhan			2016-17	0.32	Ratoon	13,750	1,10,000
				2017-18	0.32	Ratoon	12,250	98,000
				2018-19	0.26	800	10,250	82,000
5	Babubhai Ramubhai Jadhav At- Khutli	2.80	95,000- 1,10,00	2015-16	0.16	500	8,571	60,000
				2016-17	0.23	700	9,375	75,000
				2018-19	0.29	900	13,333	1,20,000
				2019-20	0.23	700	12,727	1,40,000
6	Raman Lasiyabhai Chaudhary At- Khutli	1.20	50,000- 60,000	2015-16	0.23	700	11,111	1,00,000
				2016-17	0.16	500	10,000	80,000
				2017-18	0.26	800	13,636	1,50,000
				2018-19	0.13	400	8,181	90,000
				2019-20	0.26	800	11,666	70,000
7	Manilalbhai Gayakwad At Jogvel	1.60	60,000- 70,000	2016-17	0.16	500	7,500	60,000
				2017-18	0.16	500	8,500	68,000
				2018-19	0.16	Ratoon	6,666	60,000
				2019-20	0.64	2000	22,722	2,50,000
8	Gulabbhai Ramubhai Gaikwad At- Jogvel	6.80	2,00,000- 2,50,000	2015-16	0.29	900	18,333	1,65,000
				2016-17	0.36	1100	19,375	1,55,000
				2017-18	0.36	Ratoon	16,111	1,45,000
				2018-19	0.32	1000	22,916	2,75,000
				2019-20	0.32	Ratoon	16,666	1,50,000
9	Prakashbhai Devubhai Bhusara At- Kurgam	2.00	85,000- 100,000	2019-20	0.26	800	12,000	96,000

10	Bablubhai Janiya Gamit At- Kurgam	2.80	100,000- 110,000	2017- 18		800	13,000	1,30,000
				2018- 19		800	13,636	1,50,000
				2019- 20		900	16,666	2,00,000

Please note that the income figures are approximate and may vary based on factors such as market prices and local conditions.

Source: ICAR-AICRP on Fruits, Gandevi Centre, Navsari Agricultural University (NAU), Gandevi, Gujarat (June 2022).

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Changing lives of tribal farmers in Andhra Pradesh through banana farming: a success story

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Challenge

The Horticultural Research Station in Kovvur, located in the West Godavari District of Andhra Pradesh, was established in the year 1968. Since its inception, the research station has been primarily focused on the study and development of specific crops, namely Banana and Tuber crops. Over the years, its research activities in the field of banana cultivation were significantly enhanced with the commencement of the All India Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Tropical Fruits, specifically targeting banana, starting from the year 1987.

Under this research project, various location-specific technologies were systematically developed. These technologies encompassed a wide range of aspects related to banana cultivation, such as the ideal timing for planting, optimal plant density, suitable planting methods, selection and treatment of planting materials, innovative planting systems, effective nutrient management strategies, irrigation schedules coupled with fertigation techniques, integrated weed management practices, comprehensive management of ratoon crops, and holistic disease management technologies. Additionally, cropping systems tailored for all the commercially grown banana cultivars in the state were also devised.

A fundamental aspect of the research station's mission was to disseminate these developed technologies to the wider farming community. Furthermore, under the ICAR - AICRP on Fruits, a dedicated Tribal Sub-plan (TSP) program was initiated in the year 2014-15. The primary objectives of this program were to substantially alleviate poverty and unemployment in the region, create productive assets, and generate income-generating opportunities among the tribal population. This was to be achieved through the effective and widespread dissemination of the innovative agricultural technologies developed at the research station, effectively bridging the gap between research (the source) and practical implementation in farmers' fields (the sink).

The challenges faced by the tribal population in the Kovvur region of Andhra Pradesh are significant and multifaceted. These challenges impact their economic development and overall well-being. Here's a breakdown of the key challenges mentioned:

Non-availability of Quality Planting Material:

- Access to high-quality planting material is crucial for successful agriculture. The absence of such material can hinder crop growth and productivity.

Lack of High-Yielding Varieties:

- High-yielding crop varieties are essential for increasing agricultural productivity and income. The absence of such varieties can limit farmers' potential earnings.

Poor Financial Status to Purchase Farm Inputs:

- Limited financial resources make it difficult for tribal farmers to invest in essential farm inputs like fertilizers, pesticides, and equipment. This can lead to lower crop yields.

Lack of Awareness on Improved Technologies and Its Adoption:

- Without awareness of modern agricultural practices and technologies, tribal farmers may continue to rely on traditional, less productive methods. This can hinder their ability to increase yields and income.

Dependence on Traditional Occupations:

- Many tribal populations in the region rely on traditional occupations such as craft-making, collection of forest products (leaves, honey), and shifting agriculture. These activities often provide only meager income and may not be sustainable in the long term.

Destruction of Forests:

- The destruction of forests can have adverse effects on tribal communities, as they often depend on forest resources for their livelihoods. Deforestation can lead to a loss of income and resources.

Illiteracy:

- Illiteracy can be a barrier to accessing information, education, and employment opportunities. It can also limit the ability to engage with modern agricultural practices.

Indebtedness:

- Many tribal farmers may be trapped in a cycle of debt, making it challenging to invest in their farms and improve their living conditions.

Lack of Awareness About Schemes:

- Tribal populations may not be aware of government schemes and programs designed to support their economic development. This lack of awareness can prevent them from benefiting from these initiatives.

Strict Adherence to Traditions and Customs:

While traditions and customs are important cultural aspects, strict adherence to them may hinder the adoption of modern farming practices and technologies.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes improving access to quality inputs, providing education and training on modern agricultural practices, raising awareness of government programs, and finding ways to balance traditional customs with modern needs. It also necessitates efforts to protect natural resources and forests while promoting sustainable livelihoods for tribal communities.

Initiatives:

- **Created Awareness on Scientific Cultivation of Tissue Culture Banana:**
 - This initiative likely involved educational campaigns and workshops to inform tribal farmers about the benefits of using tissue culture plants for banana cultivation. Tissue culture plants are known for their disease-free and high-yielding characteristics.
- **Conducted Training Programmes on Improved Technologies:**
 - Training programs would have provided tribal farmers with practical knowledge and skills related to modern agricultural practices and technologies. This helps them adopt more efficient farming methods.
- **Organized Field Demonstrations on Technologies through KVKs:**
 - Field demonstrations are valuable as they allow farmers to see firsthand how improved technologies work in their own fields. KVKs likely played a pivotal role in facilitating these demonstrations.
- **Supplied Quality Planting Material (Tissue Culture Plants):**
 - Providing high-quality planting material, such as tissue culture plants, ensures that farmers start with a strong foundation for their banana crop.
- **Supply of Inputs (Fertilizers/Pesticides/Biofertilisers/Micro Nutrients, etc.):**
 - Ensuring the availability of essential inputs like fertilizers, pesticides, biofertilizers, and micro nutrients supports healthy crop growth and higher yields.
- **Inculcated Timely Adoption of Management Practices:**
 - Encouraging farmers to follow recommended management practices at the right time can significantly improve crop outcomes.
- **Organized Exposure Visits of Tribal Farmers to Various National Institutes (NRCB, Trichy & IIHR, Bengaluru) for Motivation:**
 - Exposure visits are instrumental in motivating farmers by showcasing successful models and best practices implemented at prestigious national agricultural institutes.

Table 3. Key results/interesting facts

S.No	Farmer’s practice	Improved practice
1	Banana Sucker planting	Tissue culture plants
2	Poor selection of planting material	Uniform Quality planting material
3	Low population due to poor survival & establishment	Optimum population due to better survival & establishment
4	Uneven growth	Uniform growth

5	Low bunch weight & yield	Good bunch weight & yield
6	Poor quality of fruits	Better quality
7	Low market price due to poor quality	Premium price due to good quality

Impact

The implementation of scientific banana cultivation practices within the framework of the tribal sub-plan scheme, in the ITDA agency area of K R Puram jurisdiction, West Godavari district, has yielded remarkable outcomes. This initiative extended support to ten farmers across various villages in the Buttaigudem mandal. These farmers were equipped with essential resources, including high-quality banana tissue culture plants (Grand Naine variety), fertilizers, biofertilizers, micro-nutrients, and plant protection chemicals, alongside modern equipment such as sprayers. This comprehensive support facilitated the adoption of scientific management practices from the inception of cultivation through to harvest. Consequently, the results were exceptionally positive, with participating farmers experiencing significantly enhanced crop yields and the ability to command better prices in the market. On average, these farmers achieved a substantial net income ranging from Rs. 2.0 to 2.35 lakhs per hectare, in stark contrast to the comparatively modest earnings of Rs. 0.50 to 0.55 lakhs per hectare commonly observed with traditional farming methods. This notable impact underscores the transformative potential of modern agricultural techniques, backed by targeted support, in elevating both agricultural productivity and the economic prosperity of farming communities.

Table 4: Yield and Yield attributes

Particulars	Avg.bunch weight (kg)	No.of hands/bunch	No. of fruits/bunch	Yield/ha (t)
Scientific cultivation (Var.Grand Naine)	18-20	9-11	170-190	52.25
Farmer's Practice (Var.Karpoora chakkera keli)	10-12	6-7	120-130	22.00

Table 5 : Economics

Particulars	Cost of cultivation (Rs./ha)	Gross income (Rs./ha)	Net returns (Rs./ha)	C:B ratio
Scientific cultivation (Var.Grand Naine) Sale price @ Rs.7/kg	1,30,000/-	3,65,750-	2,35,750/-	1:1.81
Farmer's Practice (Var.Karpoora chakkera keli) Sale price @ Rs.5/kg	55,000/-	1,10,000/-	55,000/-	1:1.0

Key Lesson Learned:

The experience gained from working with tribal farmers in the Kovvur region has revealed critical lessons about improving their livelihoods and agricultural practices:

1. Resource Constraints: Tribal farmers face inherent challenges related to limited resources. These constraints, including access to quality inputs and financial resources, hinder their ability to adopt modern agricultural practices and achieve sustainable livelihoods.

2. Lack of Awareness: Many tribal farmers lack awareness about the benefits of adopting commercial crops and modern production technologies. Raising awareness is crucial to help them understand the potential for increased yields and income.

3. Poor Marketing Facilities: Inadequate marketing facilities and knowledge of market dynamics can lead to lower returns for tribal farmers. Effective marketing strategies and access to markets should be integrated into agricultural development initiatives.

4. Training and Education: Imparting training in improved production technologies, cropping systems, and integrated farming practices is essential. Training equips tribal farmers with the knowledge and skills needed to enhance crop yields and income.

5. Field Demonstrations and Exposure Visits: Organizing field demonstrations and exposure visits to successful farming models and national agricultural institutes can motivate tribal farmers. These firsthand experiences can inspire them to adopt innovative practices.

6. Organic Farming: Leveraging the natural organic production systems in agency areas can be an added advantage. Training tribal farmers in organic farming practices can lead to sustainable and environmentally friendly agriculture.

7. Potential for Improvement: Despite the challenges, tribal farmers have the potential to excel in agriculture and achieve standards of living on par with other progressive farmers. They can thrive with the right support, training, and access to resources.

Conclusion

the lesson learned is that by addressing the resource constraints, providing education and training, and promoting sustainable practices like organic farming, tribal farmers can significantly improve their agricultural productivity and overall quality of life. Effective intervention and support can bridge the gap and empower tribal communities to thrive in agriculture, ultimately contributing to their economic development and well-being.

Supporting Quotes and Images:

Distribution of planting material (Tc banana) & other inputs

Tribal farmers with harvested & ready for harvesting banana bunches for marketing

Additional information

Name of the village/Mandal : West Regulakunta/ Buttaigudem
Name of the District : West Godavari
Name of the Farmers : Sri. B. Satyanarayana and Sri. K. Soma Raju

Research Partners/donors : ICAR-AICRP on Fruits
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Fruit-based vegetable intercropping farming has improved the livelihoods of tribal farmers in Beisumpuikam, Peren District, Nagaland

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Introduction

The establishment of nutritional gardens in economically disadvantaged villages serves as a crucial component of agricultural development, enhancing both the livelihoods of the residents and addressing health-related issues. These gardens provide a lifeline for small-scale farmers, ensuring year-round access to nutritious food and a potential source of income. The Department of Horticulture at Nagaland University, specifically the AICRP on Fruits, Medziphema Centre, initiated a remarkable endeavor in 2020-21 under the Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP) program. This initiative involved setting up nutritional gardens featuring fruits, vegetables, spices, and indigenous medicinal plants in the backyards of local villagers. The project provided saplings, seeds, bio-inputs, and farming tools, aiming to uplift the income of these communities.

Challenges

The TSP program was conceived by the Government of India with the objective of reducing poverty, creating employment opportunities, and promoting asset creation and income generation in tribal-dominated regions. In the Nagaland districts of Dimapur and Peren, where over 80% of the population is tribal, the challenges were particularly acute. Many farmers in these areas had limited land resources, often less than one acre, and practiced traditional farming methods with crops like maize, upland rice, and common vegetables, often without the application of scientific techniques. Some resorted to backyard pig rearing for sustenance. The tribal population faced a stark reality where survival was the primary focus, with limited access to resources, a lack of awareness, and insufficient agricultural inputs.

Initiative

In 2019-20, the AICRP on Fruits, Medziphema Centre conducted a comprehensive survey of Medziphema Village and Beisumpuikam Village in Dimapur and Peren Districts to implement the TSP program effectively. The Centre identified and selected the 20 most economically vulnerable households from each village. Subsequently, the Centre organized day-long training sessions based on the survey findings. These training sessions covered various aspects of fruit crop cultivation, intercropping techniques, and livelihood improvement strategies. Additionally, the Centre distributed essential resources such as litchi and mango saplings, vegetable seeds, ginger, vermicompost, bio-pesticides, small farm tools, and sprayers to all the households. Detailed technical guidelines, provided in the local dialect, guided the beneficiaries on when, how, and what to grow.

Outputs & Outcomes:

The impact of this initiative has been promising, resulting in increased income for tribal farmers compared to their previous farming practices. Over the past two years, farmers have started harvesting vegetables from their own gardens, with expectations of additional income once litchi, mango, and lemon trees mature in the coming years. While precise income figures from the AICRP intervention are not available, visual evidence, including video clips and photos, attests to the success of the beneficiaries' efforts.

Presently, numerous unemployed youths and marginalized tribal farmers have expressed interest in the project, citing the success stories of the two villages involved. Overall, beneficiaries are elated with the program's outcomes and anticipate that it will contribute to further improvements in their social and economic statuses. This initiative not only bolsters their livelihoods but also instills hope for a brighter future in these economically challenged regions.

Photographs:

Source: ICAR-AICRP on Fruits, Medziphema Centre, Nagaland University. June 2022
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